

Kinetics of Competitive Adsorption. Part II: Chloride and Iodide Ions on Silver

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Using radioisotopes ^{131}I and ^{36}Cl the rate of adsorption of Cl^- and I^- ions on silver has been studied at $10^{-3}M$ concentration. Results show evidence of strong chemisorption in both cases, the adsorption of I^- being very much faster. Using a doubly labelled mixed adsorbate of $10^{-3}M$ NaCl and NaI solution the kinetics of competitive adsorption have been studied. While the adsorption of both the ions is mutually suppressed, that of Cl^- ion is almost wholly suppressed in the mixed adsorbate. These results have been further confirmed by a study of the desorption of adsorbed I^- and Cl^- ions from their adsorbed films of 1, 5 and 20 layer-thickness in media of water and $10^{-3}M$ NaI , NaBr and NaCl solutions. While the adsorbed I^- could not be desorbed, the adsorbed Cl^- can be progressively desorbed in NaI and NaBr solutions. The exchange desorption follows first order rate law. These results are consistent with the relative redox potentials for the electrodes Ag , AgCl(s),Cl^- and Ag , AgI(s), I^- .

The use of radioactive isotopes in the study of adsorption has yielded valuable data specially in regard to rates of adsorption and desorption at sub-micro and tracer concentrations prior to equilibrium¹⁻⁹. In addition, recent studies of simultaneous adsorption of different ions whether accompanied by exchange or not also became possible only by the use of radioactive tracers. Evidence for ionic exchange between cations of adsorbate and adsorbent is provided by the work of Palacios and Baptista¹⁰ on the adsorption of labelled Zn^{++} ions on noble metals. Willard's work¹¹ on the adsorption of labelled Na^+ ions on glass not only showed that there is an exchange of Na^+ ions but the adsorption and desorption rates are same. On the other hand, Simnad's¹² work on tracer adsorption of Pb^{++} and Bi^{+++} ions showed a partial fixing of these ions on the adsorbent surface in excess of the amount exchanged with the cations of the adsorbent.

An interesting work of tracer adsorption has been in the study of passivity of iron and chromium by Powers and Hackerman¹³, and by Schwabe and Weissmantel¹⁴. Their results

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on the adsorption of labelled anions on metal surface in the passive state revealed that the activating effect of the anion is related to its degree of adsorption. The kinetics of adsorption of the anion is, however, influenced by the degree of coverage of the metal in the passive state by oxygen as shown by the use of ^{18}O .

The application of the tracer technique for studying preferential or competitive adsorption between several adsorbate ions on a given adsorbent surface has been relatively limited. Stephens and Hackerman⁴ found that the adsorption of SO_4^{--} on Fe is markedly suppressed in the presence of Cl^- or CrO_4^{--} ions at $\text{pH} = 7$. Between CN^- and I^- ions it is the former which is more firmly adsorbed on Pt, Ni, and Ag even displacing any preadsorbed I^- ions as shown by the results of Schwabe¹⁵. In the competitive adsorption on Cu of I^- and PO_4^{---} from a mixture of $0.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution of the two ions studied by Arnikar and Mehta⁸, it is found that in the early stages most of the adsorbent sites are occupied by I^- ions, those captured by PO_4^{---} being less than 4%; this is followed after a lag of about 30 mins by a sudden and heavy adsorption of PO_4^{---} ions. It was considered interesting to extend these studies to other systems. We report here results of our study on the competitive adsorption of labelled I^- and Cl^- ions on silver. These studies have been followed by measurements of desorption rates of I^- and Cl^- ions in presence of excess of the other ion.

EXPERIMENTAL

Experimental details regarding the surface treatment of the adsorbent samples, the adsorption unit and the radioactive measurement of adsorbed anions, etc., have been described earlier^{7,8}. The silver coupons ($d = 19.9 \text{ mm}$) were annealed at 600° for an hour and chemically polished using a nitric acid bath (2 : 1 dilution) followed by washing with distilled water. The adsorbate consisting of 200 ml. of $10^{-3} M$ solutions each of NaI, NaCl and the mixture (NaI + NaCl) initially adjusted to a pH of 3.5 were maintained at 30° in a thermostat. Separate coupons were employed for each period of adsorption extending from 1 min. to 200 hr. In the case of the doubly labelled system (^{36}Cl of period $3.1 \times 10^5 \text{ yr.}$ and ^{131}I of period 8.04 days) the individual activities were determined from two measurements of the activities a_1 initial, and a_2 after 8.04 days, the two being related as follows :

$$a_1 = a_{\text{Cl}} + a_{\text{I}} \quad \dots (1)$$

$$a_2 = a_{\text{Cl}} + 0.5a_{\text{I}} \quad \dots (2)$$

Desorption with respect to mono, 5 and 20 layer thicknesses of the adsorbed Cl^- and I^- ions was studied in 100 ml of $10^{-3} M$ solutions of NaI and NaBr ($\text{pH} = 3.5$) maintained at 30° . The amount desorbed corresponds to the difference between the initial activity and the activity at time t . The factor F was calculated as the ratio of activity desorbed at time t to that desorbed at steady state. The first order rate constant k was calculated from the slope of the straight line plots of $\log(1-F)$ versus time.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The adsorption rate isotherms for I^- and Cl^- ions on Ag differ appreciably. The Cl^- ion isotherm is slightly convex towards the time axis and is continuous throughout the period studied *viz.*, 200 hr, corresponding to a maximum adsorption of about 25 layers. The isotherm for I^- ions shows marked discontinuities indicated by (i) a very sharp rise on the completion of about 100 layers of adsorption roughly in about 100 hr, and (ii) a tendency towards saturation after about 200 hr, corresponding to above 270 layers of adsorption.

In a qualitative study of the influence of pH on the adsorption of I^- and Cl^- ions on Ag it was observed that increase of H^+ concentration favours their adsorption. The Cl^- adsorption is suppressed at pH above 4 while that of I^- ions continues well upto pH = 7. It is generally assumed that in acidic media H^+ ions form the innermost potential determining layer and the anions adsorbed thereon constitute the compact Stern layer¹⁶. This model permits an interaction of the anions with the substrate metal when energetically possible as in the case of halide ions on Ag. This is consistent with Schwabe and Weissmantel's view¹⁵ that the adsorption of I^- on Ag is a case of chemisorption involving the formation of¹⁵ Ag^+I^- . The precise mechanism leading to the formation of Ag^+ from the adsorbent silver required for the formation of Ag^+I^- in the adsorption layer is however, not known. The following alternative mechanisms may be considered for the origin of Ag^+ ions.

(1) As in the phenomenon of metal corrosion, anodic and cathodic sites are formed which are either permanently separated or are continuously shifting¹⁷. In the case of silver in contact with the adsorbate, Ag^+ is formed at the anodic site by the reaction

The released electron could react with either (a) dissolved oxygen at the cathodic site to form OH^- by the reaction

or (b) H_2 may be evolved at the cathodic site by the reaction

In either case the pH of the medium goes up. This has actually been observed in our experiments.

(2) Alternatively, under favourable redox conditions, silver may directly yield Ag^+ by transferring the electron to an hydrogen ion in the medium

The formation of molecular hydrogen in (1b) and in (2) being in trace amounts may escape detection. Mechanism (1a) would appear to be more probable.

According to Campbell¹⁸, however, even in the case of a noble metal like Pt, the reaction $Pt \rightarrow Pt^{++} + 2e^-$ is considered possible at low pH (1-3). This results in a greater concentration of cations close to the surface of the metal permitting it to be covered more densely with the anions of the adsorbate. Thus on this view, mechanism (2) would appear to be equally important.

The formation of adsorption layers of the type SO_4^{--} on Fe^4 and of CN^- and I^- on noble metals¹⁵ has been postulated by earlier workers although the precise mechanism of the formation of the corresponding cations of the adsorbent metal required for such adsorption layers has not been stated. Specifically, Dreyer and Dreyer¹⁹ postulate the formation of CuI in the adsorption layer in the case of copper and an iodide solution similar to the system under study.

Campbell further considers that the binding may be due to chemisorption where the anion (I^-) can form insoluble compound as in our present system. Such a view has been postulated by Schwabe¹⁵ as well. The chemisorbed Ag^+I^- layer may develop into insoluble AgI and $(\text{AgI}_2)^-$ complex with the progressive increase in adsorption. The occurrence of a chemical reaction of this type has to be assumed to account for the multilayer adsorption observed. The high adsorption of I^- ions leading to chemisorption (Ag^+I^-) may be expected to open up crevices and grain boundaries which constitute new adsorption sites responsible for the sudden rise observed in the I^- adsorption on the completion of about 100 layers.

The greater and preferential adsorption of I^- over Cl^- ions on Ag is consistent with the standard oxidation potentials of the electrode $\text{Ag}, \text{AgX(s)}, \text{X}^-$ which is -0.2224 V for $\text{X} = \text{Cl}$ and $+0.1522$ V for $\text{X} = \text{I}$.

Thus it may be seen that Ag adsorbs I^- ions more strongly than Cl^- ions. This tendency for the preferential adsorption of I^- ions is even more distinctly brought out in the competitive adsorption of the two anions from the doubly labelled mixed adsorbate, 10^{-3} M in respect of either ion. Results showed the activity of the adsorbed layers was exclusively due to that of ^{131}I showing that the adsorption of Cl^- ions is completely suppressed and hence is not shown in Fig. 1, while all the Ag sites are occupied by I^- ions. The extent of this (I^-) adsorption is also greatly suppressed by the presence of Cl^- ions as indicated by the total adsorption of only about 60 layers of I^- ions in 200 hr (Fig. 1C) compared to 270 layers in the same time in the absence of Cl^- ions (Fig. 1A). In addition the rate-adsorption isotherm of I^- ions in the mixed adsorbate (Fig. 1C) shows step-like discontinuities at approximately 30 hr intervals.

The above findings on competitive adsorption between I^- and Cl^- ions were further confirmed by their desorption studies which led to the following results. (i) I^- ions adsorbed on Ag are not desorbed in 10^{-3} M solution of NaCl over a period of even 100 hr. This supports the conclusion mentioned above that I^- ions form a stable chemisorbed layer on Ag, not replaceable by Cl^- ions of lower oxidation potential, (ii) Cl^- ions adsorbed on Ag to 1, 5 or 20 layer-thickness are progressively desorbed in a medium of water, NaBr or NaI solutions of 10^{-3} M concentration, even at a pH of 3.5 favourable for Cl^- adsorption.

Results of our kinetic study presented in Table 1 show that (i) the rate of desorption of Cl^- ions from adsorbed layer of different thicknesses (k_n) in any medium is in the order $k_1 > k_5 > k_{20}$. This suggests that the desorption from the multilayers is slower being diffusion dependent. (ii) Generally the plot of $\log(1-F)$ versus time, F being the fraction desorbed, is made up of two linear segments, corresponding to two different rate constants for the early and the late stages of desorption. The first segment passes through the origin

showing thereby that the initial exchange desorption is a simple homogeneous first order reaction while the onset of a secondary mechanism at a later stage leads to a different rate constant.²⁰ (iii) The rate of desorption in NaI medium is generally slower for the first segment than the rate in NaBr medium for both 1 and 20 layer-thickness. For the second segment, however, the desorption is faster in iodide medium for all the layer thicknesses.

TABLE I

Rate constants for the desorption of Cl⁻ ions adsorbed on silver

Layer-thickness	Desorption medium	Rate constant $k(\text{min}^{-1})$	
		Segment-I	Segment-II
1	Water	1.7×10^{-3}	3.1×10^{-4}
	NaI $10^{-3} M$	1.7×10^{-1}	4.6×10^{-1}
	NaBr $10^{-3} M$	6.5×10^{-1}	2.4×10^{-1}
5	NaI $10^{-3} M$	$3.8 \times 10^{-1*}$	3.5×10^{-2}
	NaBr $10^{-3} M$	3.0×10^{-2}	
20	NaI $10^{-3} M$	3.0×10^{-3}	5.4×10^{-3}
	NaBr $10^{-3} M$	$5.1 \times 10^{-3*}$	

* There is only one single slope.

For comparison the desorption of labelled Cl⁻ ions was studied in water and NaCl solutions. Results show that the desorption in water also follows two mechanisms and generally the rate constants are much lower than those in NaI and NaBr solutions. In the case of NaCl solution no desorption of the labelled Cl⁻ ions was detected in $10^{-3} M$ NaCl medium showing thereby that there is no measurable isotope exchange between Cl⁻ ions of the medium and the chemisorbed Cl⁻ ion of Ag⁺.Cl⁻.

The use of water free from dissolved oxygen and water saturated with oxygen would help in verifying the merit of mechanism (1a). A careful study of the adsorption rates over a range of temperatures would also help substantiate the ionic nature of the adsorption layer postulated. Work on these lines is in progress.

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